

Whole Genome Sequencing (ONT):

Human Variation Project

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Version	0.1		

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Executive Summary

The aims of this analysis were to detect and compare SNPs, INDELS and structural variants (SVs) in sample A, B and C that were run on a PromethION flowcell by itself (1x), run on a flowcell with another sample (2x) and run on a flowcell with two other samples (3X). Three samples were tested: 57 (named Sample A), 73 (named Sample B) and 109 (named Sample C). The workflow used can be downloaded from www.zenodo.org/communities/DIPLOMICS Method Development ([DIPLOMICS Method PromethION Human WGS workflow v0.1 13 10 2024](https://zenodo.org/records/13102024)).

Input Data

Sequencing data was generated through ONT sequencing on the PromethION 24 (P24) for each sample and for each condition (1X, 2X, 3X) (see [DIPLOMICS Method PromethION Human WGS workflow v0.1 13 10 2024](https://zenodo.org/records/13102024) for the lab protocol followed). Concatenated FASTQ files from each experimental variable sample were prepared. Table 1 lists the sequencing outputs of each sample.

Analytical Procedures

1. Read quality assessment and pre-processing:

ONT reads were quality checked and low-quality bases were trimmed with the Nanofilt (Wouter *et al.*,2018) package. Only reads longer than 200bp and with minimum average read quality score (Q) >10 were selected in the filtering step. Ten bp were trimmed from both start and end of the reads. Table 1 lists the sequencing output before and after filtering in addition to the average coverage per sample. Quality checks were performed before and after trimming using Nanoplot (Wouter *et al.*,2018) and output metrics are recorded separately per sample (Tables 2-4).

2. Mapping:

Filtered reads were mapped to the human genome sequence GRCh38 with the software package Minimap2 (Li,2018). Mapped reads were then converted to bam files and sorted for use using samtools (Danecek *et al.*,2021). The bam output files were analysed directly in the next step. The 1x datasets were also downsampled to 20x, 15x and 10x average coverage using samtools depth.

3. Variant calling:

Variant calling using the sorted bam files from the mapping step were called with the software package Clair3 (Zheng *et al.*,2021) for single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and INDELS. Sniffles2 (Smolka *et al.*,2024) was used to identify structural variants. To determine the overlapping and distinct mutations and/or structural variants shared between the sample run on different condition, vcftools-compare from vcftools (Danecek *et al.*,2011) was used to generate Venn diagrams. Figures 1 to 3 show SNPs, INDELS and structural variants identified by Clair3 and Sniffles2 respectively, comparing 1X, 2X and 3X data sets for Sample A,B and C respectively .

The percent similarities of each variant type (SNPs, INDELS and structural variants) were identified across the datasets for each sample.

To calculate the percentage similarity between variants identified in the one sample on a flow cell dataset (1X) and in the same sample downsampled to either 19-20x, 15X and 10X average coverage, the following formulae were used (percentage is indicated in black and two stars **):

$$\text{Percentage similarity} = (\text{Variants common to downsampled and 1X datasets} / \text{All variants found in 1x dataset}) * 100$$

To calculate the percentage similarity between variants identified in the 2X and 3X datasets in comparison to the datasets downsampled from the 1X sequencing reads to the corresponding coverage (approximately 15-20X and 10X coverage respectively, see Table 5), one of the following formulae were used (percentage is indicated in red and one star *):

$$\text{Percentage similarity} = (\text{Variants common to 2X and downsampled dataset from 1X corresponding to equivalent coverage} / \text{All variants found in 2X}) * 100$$

Or

$$\text{Percentage similarity} = (\text{Variants common to 3X and downsampled dataset from 1X corresponding to equivalent coverage} / \text{All variants found in 3X}) * 100$$

Results from these comparisons are found in Tables 6-8 (Sample A), Tables 9-11 (Sample B) and Tables 12-14 (Sample C).

RESULTS

More than 100Gb of sequencing data was created per flow cell. For the 1X samples, average coverage (Q>10) ranged from 37,14X to 38,16X. For the 2X samples, average coverage (Q>10) ranged from 16,53X to 21,06X. For the 3X samples, average coverage (Q>10) ranged from 9,67X to 10,37X (Table 1). The average quality (Q scores) of the total reads before and after trimming for the three samples were 15.3 and 17.5, respectively (Table 2-4).

Data were successfully analysed using the Oxford Nanopore wf human variation pipeline. Variants identified in the downsampled datasets (approx. 19X coverage) were compared to the 1X data set (approx. 38X coverage). On average, the percentage similarity was 91,386% for SNPs, 81,072% for INDELS and 73,805% for structural variants (Tables 6-14). Although there is a decrease in the number of variants identified at 19X average coverage in comparison to 38X coverage, the percent similarities between the 19X average coverage (downsampled from the 1X data sets) and the 2X data set, with corresponding average coverage, were high, particularly for SNPs. These preliminary results indicate that an average of 19X coverage may be sufficient for SNP identification using the workflow tested, although further optimisation of the INDEL and structural variation workflow is required. Testing of the workflow with rare disease samples is on-going.

Table 1. Sequencing and quality control results from the three samples

Sample_ID	Barcode	Samples /flow cell	Wash_reload	Bases (Gb)*	Bases_pass (Gb) Q>10 **	Coverage Gb pass / #samples / 3.4 Gb
A	NA	1	Yes	146,93	126,28	37,14
A	NB14	2	Yes	159,53	143,24	21,06
A	NB02	3	Yes	124,84	105,74	10,37
B	NA	1	Yes	150,97	129,75	38,16
B	NB16	2	Yes	136,50	120,20	17,68
B	NB21	3	Yes	110,98	98,64	9,67
C	NA	1	Yes	144,78	127,6	37,53
C	NB20	2	Yes	123,05	112,39	16,53
C	NB03	3	Yes	124,84	105,74	10,37

* Total sequencing data derived from the Sequencing Run report

**Data following Nanofilt trimming (Nanoplot output)

Table 2. Summary of ONT reads before and after filtering step for sample A.

	1x	2x	3x
Number of reads before trimming	19 192 304	11 913 318	8 204 080
Number of reads after trimming	15 623 234	9 307 428	6 149 204
Mean quality before trimming	15.9	15.6	15.3
Mean quality after trimming	17.9	17.7	17.5
Mean read length before trimming	6 580.0	5 620.2	5 163.2
Mean read length after trimming	6 833.5	6 308.6	5 808.2

Table 3. Summary of ONT reads before and after filtering step for sample B.

	1x	2x	3x
Number of reads before trimming	18 726 448	9 651 147	5 182 643
Number of reads after trimming	17 802 837	9 229 330	4 917 760
Mean quality before trimming	15.7	15.6	15.3
Mean quality after trimming	16.9	17.2	17.0
Mean read length before trimming	6928.9	5996.3	6333.8
Mean read length after trimming	7043.0	6083.9	6462.6

Table 4. Summary of ONT reads before and after filtering step for sample C.

	1x	2x	3x
Number of reads before trimming	20 843 167	7 775 158	3 616 932
Number of reads after trimming	19 861 745	7 661 307	3 535 024
Mean quality before trimming	16.1	16.3	16.0
Mean quality after trimming	17.1	17.0	17.0
Mean read length before trimming	6 122.1	6 453.6	7 356.1
Mean read length after trimming	6 216.7	6 449.1	7 324.4

Table 5. Average coverages after downsampling sample A, B and C to theoretical coverages (20X, 15X, 10X)

	Sample A coverage	Sample B coverage	Sample C coverage
20x	19.7056	20.0211	19.5683
15x	15.6819	16.0668	15.7154
10x	10.0651	10.3018	10.0917

Figure 1. SNPs, INDELs and structural variations identified in 1x, 2x and 3x data sets using Clair3 and Sniffles2 in sample A. For Sample A, 1X= 37X average coverage; 2X= 20 X average coverage; 3X=13X average coverage.

Table 6. SNP percentage similarity between sample A sequenced on a 1x, 2x and 3x flow cell and downsampled samples based on 19x, 15x and 10x coverages

	1x	2x	3x
38x	*100%	-	-
19x	**89.268%	*94.717%	-
15x		-	-
10x	**87,678%	-	*92.317%

Table 7. INDEL percentage similarity between sample A sequenced on a 1x, 2x and 3x flow cell and downsampled samples based on 19x, 15x and 10x coverages

	1x	2x	3x
38x	*100%	-	-
19x	**76,222%	*80.850%	-
15x		-	-
10x	**69,518%	-	*78.941%

Table 8. Structural variation percentage similarity between sample A sequenced on a 1x, 2x and 3x flow cell and downsampled samples based on 19x, 15x and 10x coverages

	1x	2x	3x
38x	*100%	-	-
19x	**73.286%	*62.487%	-
15x	**68.768%	-	-
10x	**56,063%	-	*53.197%

SNP Analysis – Clair3

Indel Analysis – Clair3

Figure 2. SNPs, INDELS and Structural variations identified using Clair3 and Sniffles in sample B. For Sample B, 1X= 38X average coverage; 2X= 16 X average coverage; 3X=10X average coverage.

Table 9. SNP percentage similarity between sample B sequenced on a 1x, 2x and 3x flow cell and downsampled samples based on 20x, 16x and 10x coverages

	1x	2x	3x
38x	*100%	-	-
20x	**95.643%	-	-
16x	**94.462%	*94.512%	-
10x	**91.020%	-	*89.452%

Table 10. Indel percentage similarity between sample B sequenced on a 1x, 2x and 3x flow cell and downsampled samples based on 20x, 16x and 10x coverage

	1x	2x	3x
38x	*100%	-	-
20x	**88.056%	-	-
16x	**83.718%	*79.897%	-
10x	**71.533%	-	*72.682%

Table 11. Structural variation percentage similarity between sample B sequenced on a 1x, 2x and 3x flow cell and downsampled samples based on 20x, 16x and 10x coverage

	1x	2x	3x
38x	*100%	-	-
20x	**74.070%	-	-
16x	**68.228%	*58.242%	-
10x	**56.804%	-	*58.061%

SNP Analysis - Clair3

Indel Analysis - Clair3

Structural Variation Analysis - Sniffles

Figure 3. SNPs, INDELS and structural variations identified in 1x, 2x and 3x using Clair3 and Sniffles in sample C. For Sample C, 1X= 39X average coverage; 2X= 15 X average coverage; 3X=10X average coverage.

Table 12. SNP percentage similarity between sample C sequenced on a 1x, 2x and 3x flow cell and downsampled samples based on 19x, 15x and 10x coverages

	1x	2x	3x
39x	*100%	-	-
19x	**89.248%	-	-
15x	**88.813%	*94.161%	-
10x	**88.047%	-	*71.593%

Table 13. Indel percentage similarity between sample C sequenced on a 1x, 2x and 3x flow cell and downsampled samples based on 19x, 16x and 10x coverage

	1x	2x	3x
39x	*100%	-	-
19x	**78.940%	-	-
15x	**75.785%	*79.0573%	-
10x	**74.625%	-	*58.090%

Table 14. Structural variation percentage similarity between sample C sequenced on a 1x, 2x and 3x flow cell and downsampled samples based on 19x, 15x and 10x coverage

	1x	2x	3x
39x	*100%	-	-
19x	**74.059%	-	-
15x	**67.749%	*56.775%	-
10x	**56.802%	-	*41.549%

Tools used

- NanoPlot
- NanoFilt
- Samtools
- Clair3
- Sniffles
- Vcftools

Computer hardware

All analysis were done on a 10 CPU High Performance cluster with 144GB RAM running.

Code

A nextflow script and R script are attached to the report. The code is well commented and documented, ensuring that the entire analysis can be performed again with identical results.

Attachments

- QC txt and html summary statistics report for each sample - NanoPlot-report.html, NanoStats.txt.
- 2 .vcf files for each sample - merge_output.vcf.gz (Clair3), Output.vcf (Sniffles)
- Nextflow pipeline script – Main.nf.
- Vcf comparison files
- Supplementary excel file

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Version	Date revised	Significant changes	Next review date	Author
0.1	04 April 2024	Document created		P Swart
0.1	15 May 2024	Report		S Taukobong